

Teachers' Occupational Stress and Performance

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Abstract:

A variety of internal and external factors influence the quality of teaching performance. Understanding these factors and their interplay is crucial for enhancing teaching effectiveness and ensuring positive educational outcomes. In this context, this study aimed to determine the level of occupational stress of teachers in relation to their level of performance in one of the districts of a medium-sized division in a highly urbanized city in Central Philippines during the School Year 2021-2022. A quantitative research design, precisely a descriptive approach, was utilized with a sample of 201 teachers selected through stratified random sampling and Cochran's formula. On occupational stress, teachers identified high stress levels in the areas of instruction management and working environment, with moderate levels in curricular and extracurricular activities. Subsequent analysis indicated that when grouped according to age, civil status, and length of service, teachers demonstrated outstanding performance during the School Year 2021-2022. Significant differences were found in teachers' occupational stress levels based on their Educational Attainment, plantilla position, and civil status. The results concluded a substantial relationship between occupational stress and teachers' performance. These findings underscore the importance of professional development opportunities focused on stress management and coping mechanisms, teaching strategies enhancement, classroom management, and the latest educational research that could help minimize stress.

Keywords: Teacher's well-being, occupational stress, performance, public school teachers, Negros Occidental, Philippines.

Introduction:

Nature of the Problem

Teaching performance primarily involves the capability to execute the described duties and responsibilities associated with a particular role or position. The quality of teaching performance is influenced by both internal and external factors, including the environment, social interactions, and personal motivation.

Consequently, the complete implementation of the Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013 in the Philippines, also known as Republic Act 10533, which mandates 12 years of basic education, has resulted in significant changes to the job responsibilities of teachers (Romero & Bantigue, 2016).

With educational system improvements, teachers now face higher expectations, handling tasks like paperwork, managing diverse student behavior, attending seminars, and meeting reporting/training requirements. This increased workload has been linked to psychological issues such as occupational stress, job dissatisfaction, and disengagement, thus affecting performance. Occupational stress can influence a teacher's ability to perform effectively in the classroom. They may need help delivering high-quality instruction, managing classroom behavior, and providing adequate student support.

Current State of Knowledge

Ayub et al. (2018) investigated the factors contributing to work stress in primary school teachers. The goal was to determine the effect of work stress on teacher performance. The authors argue that work stress impacts their concentration in teaching, weakens their power, and affects student-teacher relations and motivation.

It has been found that teachers' stress is a reaction to unwanted environmental factors. Furthermore, the performance of teachers is both task and non-task-related (Anwar & Sadaf, 2012). Every employee faces workplace stress. It happens when the workload exceeds the employees' ability to perform and complete the job. Stress occurs when too much pressure at work is not managed correctly. Occupational stress is caused by various factors (Manalo, 2018).

Anyanwu et al. (2015) studied how poor working conditions, teacher pressure, and other factors impact teacher performance, regardless of gender. Moreover, a research study investigated how Teaching difficulties and feelings

of pressure at work significantly contributed to teachers' stress. These factors encompass teachers' daily challenges, such as managing classroom behavior, meeting diverse student needs, preparing lesson plans, and handling administrative tasks. (Ssenyonga & Tobias, 2021).

Torreón and Trabajo's (2018) study indicates that teachers experience greater occupational stress than post-graduate or unskilled teachers. Punia and Balda (2016) reported that many teachers employed by the Central Board of School Education (CBSE) experience moderate stress levels. This stress is primarily attributed to factors such as role overload, role ambiguity, role conflict, lack of control, poor peer relations, and strenuous working conditions.

Kimama (2023) acknowledges the influence of stress and burnout on their performance. The study illustrates the adverse effects reported by teachers, including low output, poor delivery in class, demotivation, lack of concentration, and disorganization. The study of Mingoa (2017) emphasizes that stressors and coping strategies help teachers and would-be teachers prepare for factors that could cause stress in the workplace and potentially affect classroom performance.

Sumanga et al. (2022) research has identified that educational attainment and the number of attended training sessions significantly influence teaching performance. Teachers with more relevant training and higher educational qualifications tend to achieve better teaching outcomes. Another research examined the predictor of teaching performance among the components of work-related stress in 210 randomly selected elementary and secondary public school teachers in Angeles City. The author highlights that the higher level of demand, a subcomponent of stress, can result in lower teaching performance (Collantes, 2020).

Theoretical Underpinnings

The stress mindset theory encompasses individuals' beliefs regarding the outcomes of encountering stress. This involves believing that stress can have positive effects, known as a stress-is-enhancing mindset, and the opposing belief that stress can have negative consequences, termed a stress-is-debilitating mindset. These beliefs pertain to various aspects, such as health and vitality, performance and productivity, and learning and growth (Crum et al., 2013).

The Yerkes-Dodson law is a model that illustrates the relationship between stress and task performance. According to this law, individuals achieve their peak performance at an intermediate level of stress or arousal. This means that moderate stress can enhance performance by providing motivation and focus. However, when the stress level is too low, individuals may need more drive and energy to perform well. Conversely, when the stress level is too high, it can lead to anxiety and overwhelm, thereby impairing performance. This concept is also referred to as the inverted U model of arousal. It is visually represented by a U-shaped curve where performance increases with arousal to a certain point, after which it declines with further increases in arousal. (Teigen, 1994). This model also demonstrates why teacher stress is relevant and should be investigated further by demonstrating clear linkages between teacher stress and teacher outcomes and performance.

Consequently, this study aimed to ascertain whether occupational stress based on the theories mentioned impacted teachers' performance. The findings of this study may be helpful to administrators and faculty developers as they choose how to allocate resources and construct programs.

Objectives of the Study

This study aimed to determine the level of occupational stress of teachers in relation to their level of performance in one of the districts of a medium-sized division in a highly urbanized city in Central Philippines during the School Year 2021-2022. Specifically, it aimed to determine: 1) the teacher's level of occupational stress associated with the management of instruction, curricular and extracurricular activities, and working environment; 2) the level of performance of the public elementary school teachers during the School Year 2021-2022 when grouped according to the aforementioned age, civil status, Educational Attainment, plantilla position, length of service, and family income; 3) the significant difference in the level of occupational stress of teachers when grouped according to the aforementioned variables; 4) the significant difference in the level of performance of teachers when grouped according to the aforementioned variables; and 5) the significant relationship between the levels of occupational stress and performance of the teachers.

Research Methodology:

The study's methodology-related components, such as the research design, respondents, research instrument, data collection process, and ethical issues, are described in this part.

Research Design

This study employed a descriptive research design to determine the level of occupational stress and its relation to teacher performance. According to Nassaji (2015), descriptive research aims to describe a phenomenon and its

characteristics. This study is more concerned with what happened rather than how or why it happened. As a result, observation and survey tools are frequently used to collect data. Descriptive research is particularly useful when researchers want to better understand a topic, establish baseline data, or identify patterns or trends.

Respondents

This paper used stratified random sampling to determine the respondents, courtesy of the Cochran formula (N=419; n=201).

Instrument

This study used a self-made questionnaire to gather all the data, mainly from teacher respondents. The questionnaire was divided into two parts: Part 1 contains queries on respondents' profiles such as age, civil status, educational attainment, plantilla position, length of service, and Family Income, while Part 2 contains the questionnaire proper on the teacher's level of occupational stress with eight-line items each for management of instruction, curricular & extracurricular activities, and working environment. Each item was rated on a scale of 1 to 5, using a 5-point Likert scale rating with 5 as Always, 4 Often, 3 as Sometimes, 2 as Rarely, and 1 as Almost Never.

Procedures for Data Collection

The data-gathering procedure for the study involved obtaining approval from the Schools Division Superintendent via a letter request. Accordingly, a letter request was sent to the school heads, and upon approval, the researcher scheduled the questionnaire's administration for the respondents and the researcher in a mutually convenient manner. The link to the Google Form of the survey questionnaire was sent to the respective School Heads of each school for dissemination. The researcher administered and retrieved the study instrument to ensure 100% retrieval. The researcher assured the respondents that all data gathered in this study was treated with the utmost confidentiality. Following data retrieval, it was tabulated, analyzed, and interpreted based on the specific challenges mentioned in this study. Each respondent's scores were encoded according to variables, and the computations were performed using SPSS software. Likewise, statistical tables were constructed based on the objectives stated in the study.

Data Analysis/ Statistical Treatment

Objectives 1-2 used the descriptive analytical scheme and mean as statistical tools to determine the level of occupational stress of teachers in managing instruction, curricular and extracurricular activities, working environment, and teachers' performance when grouped according to variables. Objectives 3-4 used the comparative analytical scheme and Mann-Whitney U-Test to determine whether a significant difference exists in teachers' occupational stress levels when grouped according to selected variables and the significant difference in the level of teachers' performance when grouped according to the same variables. Finally, objective 5 utilized a relational analytical scheme and Spearman Rho to determine whether there is a significant relationship between teachers' levels of occupational stress performance.

Ethical Considerations

The research study adhered to strict ethical guidelines to safeguard the respondents' safety, welfare, and confidentiality. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, and their data were anonymized and stored securely. Care was taken in data collection and processing, focusing on accuracy and reliability. Participants' health and safety were prioritized, and support services were provided if needed. The study received approval from an institutional review board or ethics committee, and any changes were subjected to ethical review and approval.

Results and Discussion

This deals with the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of data gathered to carry out the objectives of this study. All these were made possible by following certain procedures to give the exact data and solution to each problem.

Level of Occupational Stress of Public Elementary School Teachers in Management of Instruction, Curricular and Extra Curricular Activities, and Working Environment

Table 1
Level of Occupational Stress of Public Elementary School Teachers in Management of Instruction

Management of Instruction Items	Mean	Interpretation
<i>As a teacher, I am stressed with</i> 1. keeping the classroom disciplined and orderly.	3.59	High Level

2. handling unmotivated pupils.	3.60	High Level
3. having to deal with restless or misbehaving children.	3.73	High Level
4. keeping each pupil in the classroom in a pleasant attitude.	3.62	High Level
5. addressing the special needs of the students.	3.61	High Level
6. the lack of time to spend with individual learners.	3.49	Moderate Level
7. using the right method/strategy to address learning gaps.	3.57	High Level
8. students who are not ready to learn the lesson.	3.54	High Level
Overall Mean	3.59	High Level

Table 1 illustrates the level of occupational stress of public elementary school teachers in the area of instruction management, with an overall mean score of 3.59, which is interpreted as a high level. Moreover, it revealed that item 3, "Having to deal with restless or misbehaving children," obtained the highest mean score of 3.73, interpreted as "high level." In contrast, item 6, "The lack of time to spend with individual learners," obtained the lowest mean score of 3.49, which is interpreted as a "moderate level."

The data suggests that poor student conduct and misbehavior within the classroom have been connected to a decline in the occupational well-being of teachers. These behaviors can create a hostile and distracting learning environment, making it challenging for teachers to effectively deliver their lessons and manage their classrooms.

This is supported by a research study conducted by Aldrup et al. (2018) on student misbehavior and teacher well-being, which emphasized that poor student conduct has been connected to a decline in occupational well-being.

Table 2
Level of Occupational Stress of Public Elementary School Teachers in Curricular and Extracurricular Activities
Curricular and Extra Curricular Activities

Items	Mean	Interpretation
<i>As a teacher, I am stressed with</i>		
1. carrying out educational responsibilities and spending time with my family.	3.49	Moderate Level
2. conducting trips with pupils.	2.92	Moderate Level
3. working with too diverse classrooms (different cognitive levels).	3.41	Moderate Level
4. having inspections or evaluative situations in the classroom	3.63	High Level
5. helping a child with poor academic results to progress.	3.71	High Level
6. preparing students for competitions outside of school hours.	3.40	Moderate Level
7. congested topics and lessons prescribed by the curriculum.	3.76	High Level
8. organizing programs and activities to benefit learners.	3.57	High Level
Overall Mean	3.49	Moderate Level

Table 2 shows the level of occupational stress of the public elementary school teachers in the area of curricular and extracurricular activities with an overall mean score of 3.49, interpreted as a moderate level. Item 7, which reads, "Congested topics and lesson prescribed by the curriculum," registered the highest mean score of 3.76, interpreted as high level. In contrast, item no. 2, which reads, "Conducting trips with pupils," obtained the lowest mean score of 2.92, interpreted as a moderate level.

It suggests that teachers are overburdened by the vast quantity of material or subjects they must cover in a particular period. Teachers struggle to strike a balance between completing curricular requirements and giving their students engaging, productive learning opportunities.

This finding was confirmed by Chaudhari (2023), whose study emphasized that a curriculum that is very rigidly structured and overloaded with topics can have serious consequences for student learning, teacher well-being, and educational quality. With extra administrative responsibilities, the burden of organizing, executing, and evaluating classes might become too much to handle. This constant strain has the potential to cause emotional weariness and a reduction in overall work satisfaction over time. As a result, these responsibilities can impede teachers' ability to make sound decisions and maintain focus, largely due to insufficient rest, which hinders their readiness to work efficiently the following day.

Table 3
Level of Occupational Stress of Public Elementary School Teachers in Working Environment

Working Environment		
Items	Mean	Interpretation
<i>As a teacher, I am stressed with</i>		
1. teaching in noisy conditions.	3.71	High Level

2. teaching in unsuitable thermal conditions.	3.81	High Level
3. the classrooms that needed major/minor repair.	3.72	High Level
4. the shortage of equipment and school facilities	3.81	High Level
5. the lack of resource materials for lessons.	3.86	High Level
6. not having enough physical space for activities inside/outside the classroom.	3.82	High Level
7. the lack of school safety protocols for teachers, students	3.41	Moderate Level
8. the unsafe community to which the school belongs.	3.19	Moderate Level
Overall Mean	3.66	High Level

Table 3 reveals the level of occupational stress of the public elementary school teachers in the area working environment with an overall mean score of 3.66, interpreted as a high level.

Item 5, which reads, "The lack of resource materials for lessons," obtained the highest mean score of 3.86, which is interpreted as a high level. In contrast, item 8, which reads, "The unsafe community to which the school belongs," obtained the the lowest mean score of 3.19, interpreted as a moderate level.

This reveals that teachers regard the lack of resource materials as a great stressor. The materials, tools, and technologies required to support learning may not be available to teachers and students without sufficient resources. It highlights the importance of providing teachers with the necessary resources to effectively deliver their lessons and manage their classrooms.

This is supported by a research study on the correlation between a lack of educators' access to resources needed and higher stress levels. The study highlights teachers who lack the tools necessary to provide high-quality education experience greater levels of job-related stress, which has a detrimental effect on student progress if working conditions do not adequately support teachers through trying times (McCarthy, 2019).

Level of Performance of Public Elementary School Teachers when Grouped according to variables

Table 4

Level of Performance of Public Elementary School Teachers when grouped according to variables

Variables	Category	Mean	Interpretation
Age	Younger	4.52	Outstanding
	Older	4.55	Outstanding
Civil Status	Single	4.55	Outstanding
	Married	4.52	Outstanding
Educational Attainment	Lower	4.43	Very Satisfactory
	Higher	4.68	Outstanding
Length of Service	Shorter	4.51	Outstanding
	Longer	4.57	Outstanding
Plantilla Position	Lower	4.48	Very Satisfactory
	Higher	4.65	Outstanding
Family Income	Lower	4.49	Very Satisfactory
	Higher	4.60	Outstanding

Table 4 presents the level of performance of the public elementary school teachers during the school year 2021-2022, and it was revealed that the performance rating of the public elementary school teachers within the variables age, civil status, length of service, and plantilla position in both groups of respondents, received outstanding mean scores. On the other hand, teachers who have lower educational attainment, are in lower plantilla positions, and have lower Family Incomes all received very satisfactory performance ratings, with mean scores of 4.43, 4.48, and 4.49, respectively.

This reveals that public elementary school teachers can perform well under certain circumstances, regardless of their demographic characteristics. It can be deduced from the results of this study that the teachers have consistently demonstrated great performance despite their occupational stress, which may have contributed to their performance. It was also shown that educational attainment, plantilla position, and family income play a crucial role in determining how well teachers can do their job and meet the expectations of their school. Sumanga et al. (2022) support this, concluding that a teacher with higher educational attainment and more relevant training tends to perform better in teaching. By considering these factors, educators can better understand the strengths and weaknesses of their teachers and develop targeted strategies to support their professional growth and development.

Comparative Analysis in the Level of Occupational Stress of Public Elementary School Teachers in Management of Instruction, Curricular and Extra Curricular Activities, and Working Environment when grouped According to Age, Civil Status, Educational Attainment, Length of Service, Plantilla Position, and Family Income

Table 5

Differences in the Level of Occupational Stress of Public Elementary School Teachers in Management of Instruction When Grouped and Compared According to Variables

Management of Instruction							
Variables	Categories	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U - test	Sig. Level	p-value	Interpretation
Age	Younger	106	97.90	4706.5	0.424	0.424	Not Significant
	Older	95	104.46				
Civil Status	Single	73	90.38	3896.5	0.050	0.050	Significant
	Married	128	107.06				
Educational Attainment	Lower	120	113.60	3347.5	0.05	0.000	Significant
	Higher	81	82.33				
Length of Service	Shorter	112	94.64	4272.0	0.082	0.082	Not Significant
	Longer	89	109.00				
Plantilla Position	Lower	140	106.41	3512.0	0.045	0.045	Significant
	Higher	61	88.57				
Family Income	Lower	127	103.91	4330.0	0.353	0.353	Not Significant
	Higher	74	96.01				

Table 5 presents the difference in the level of occupational stress of public elementary school teachers in the management of instruction when grouped according to different variables. When grouped according to civil status and Educational Attainment, significant differences were observed as the computed p-values of 0.050 and 0.000 were all lower than the significance level of 0.05. The null hypothesis is henceforth rejected.

This implies that the teachers' occupational stress in the management of instruction is influenced by their civil status, Educational Attainment, and plantilla position. The study suggests that teachers' occupational stress in managing instruction is shaped by their personal and professional characteristics. Specifically, single teachers tend to experience less stress than their married counterparts. In comparison, teachers who have pursued higher education levels tend to experience more stress compared to those with lower educational attainment. Additionally, teachers in lower positions tend to experience more significant occupational stress than those in higher positions.

On the contrary, when respondents were grouped according to age, length of service, and average family income, it showed no significant difference as the computed p-values of 0.424, 0.082, and 0.353, respectively, both higher than the 0.05 level of significance, interpreted as "not significant." Hence, the hypothesis is accepted.

This is further supported by research by Sharma (2020), which found that teachers' occupational stress in controlling the teaching process is highly influenced by their civil status. Moreover, it was also revealed that married women experience more conflict in their personal and professional lives than men do. They also bear a greater burden of responsibility than their partners in life. This research study also concludes that there is a significant relationship between stress levels and employees' incomes. The employee that has less income suffers from high stress and has high-stress levels as compared to the one that has a high income.

The result is also affirmed by Elliot (2021), emphasizing that being the ones who impart information and design the curricula, teachers are extremely important to students' education. In a classroom full of children with a range of skills, teachers support academic instruction, behavior management, and social-emotional learning. Research indicates that the most important factor is the quality of the teacher. This is an element that contributes to increasing student performance (Gagnon et al., 2015). Stress makes it harder for instructors to create great learning environments and effective teaching strategies, which has a detrimental impact on students' social, emotional, behavioral, and academic results (Bottiani et al., 2019).

Table 6

Differences in the Level of Occupational Stress of Public Elementary School Teachers in Curricular and Extracurricular Activities When Grouped According to Variables

Curricular and Extra Curricular Activities							
Variables	Categories	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U - test	Sig. Level	p-value	Interpretation
Age	Younger	106	96.56	4564.0		0.252	Not Significant
	Older	95	105.96				
Civil Status	Single	73	96.34	4332.0		0.390	Not Significant
	Married	128	103.66				
Educational Attainment	Lower	120	111.96	3544.5	0.05	0.001	Significant
	Higher	81	84.76				
Length of Service	Shorter	112	94.41	4245.5		0.071	Not Significant
	Longer	89	109.30				
Plantilla Position	Lower	140	106.51	3499.0		0.042	Significant
	Higher	61	88.36				
Family Income	Lower	127	106.53	3996.5		0.077	Not Significant

Table 6 shows the difference in the level of occupational stress of public elementary school teachers in curricular and extracurricular activities. When respondents were grouped according to Educational Attainment and plantilla position, significant differences were observed with *p*-values of 0.001 and 0.042, respectively, all lower than the 0.05 level of significance, which were interpreted as "significant." The null hypothesis is, therefore, rejected. On the contrary, when respondents are grouped according to age, civil status, length of service, and average family income, with *p*-values of 0.252, 0.390, 0.071, and 0.077, respectively, all higher than the 0.05 level of significance, interpreted as "not significant." Hence, accepting the hypothesis.

This implies that the educational attainment and plantilla position of a teacher influence the occupational stress they experience in curricular and extracurricular activities. Moreover, the teachers' level of occupational stress in curricular and extracurricular activities is not influenced by the teachers' age, civil status, length of service, and Family Income.

Galanakis et al. (2020) emphasize that there are higher stress levels among teachers who have not received a master's degree, while tenure did not play a significant role. This also runs counter to a study by Spiromitros and Iordanidis (2017) that found stress levels are lower in bachelor's degree holders than in master's degree holders.

Table 7
Differences in the Level of Occupational Stress of Public Elementary School Teachers in Working Environment When Grouped According to Variables

Working Environment							
Variables	Categories	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U - test	Sig. Level	p-value	Interpretation
Age	Younger	106	98.08	4725.5		0.452	Not Significant
	Older	95	104.26				
Civil Status	Single	73	100.00	4599.0		0.854	Not Significant
	Married	128	101.57				
Educational Attainment	Lower	120	105.67	4299.5	0.05	0.165	Not Significant
	Higher	81	94.08				
Length of Service	Shorter	112	95.58	4377.0		0.138	Not Significant
	Longer	89	107.82				
Plantilla Position	Lower	140	106.62	3483.0		0.038	Significant
	Higher	61	88.10				

Family Income	Lower	127	106.30	4026.5	0.090	Not Significant
	Higher	74	91.91			

Table 7 indicates the difference in the level of occupational stress of public elementary school teachers in the working environment. When respondents were grouped according to plantilla position, there was a significant difference with a p -value of 0.038, which is lower than the 0.05 level of significance. Hence rejecting the hypothesis. Nonetheless, when respondents are grouped according to age, civil status, Educational Attainment, length of service, and average family income, the computed p -values of 0.452, 0.854, 0.165, 0.138, and 0.090 were found to be more than the level of significance of 0.05, indicating that the research finding does support the initial hypothesis.

This implies a correlation between the plantilla position of a teacher and the level of occupational stress experienced in the realm of working conditions. Moreover, it signifies that teachers' level of occupational stress in the working environment is not influenced by their age, civil status, Educational Attainment, length of service, and Family Income.

This result is validated by Alson (2019), who emphasized that teachers experienced stress that was brought on by hazardous working conditions and a lack of materials and resources to do their tasks effectively.

This negates the study of Torreon and Trabajo (2018), which reveals that teachers exhibit higher occupational stress than post-graduate or unskilled teachers. Teachers with 6-10 years of experience endure the highest occupational stress, while those with 0-5 years face the least, with the remaining two categories lying somewhere in between. There are no significant disparities in monthly salary, subjects taught, marital status, or occupational stress among secondary school teachers, according to the findings.

Comparative Analysis in the Level of Self-Efficacy of Public Elementary School Teachers in terms of Instruction, Discipline, and Social and Community Involvement when Grouped by Age, Civil Status, Educational Attainment, Length of Service, Plantilla Position, and Family Income

Table 8
Differences in the Level of Performance of Public Elementary School Teachers When Grouped According to Variables

Variables	Categories	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U - test	Sig. Level	P-value	Interpretation
Age	Younger	106	99.14	4837.5		0.631	Not Significant
	Older	95	103.08				
Civil Status	Single	73	106.48	4272.0		0.313	Not Significant
	Married	128	97.88				
Educational Attainment	Lower	120	80.65	2417.5	0.05	0.000	Significant
	Higher	81	131.15				
Length of Service	Shorter	112	96.72	4504.5		0.241	Not Significant
	Longer	89	106.39				
Plantilla Position	Lower	140	90.09	2743.0		0.000	Significant
	Higher	61	126.03				
Family Income	Lower	127	92.85	3663.5		0.009	Significant

Table 8 indicates the difference in the level of performance of public elementary school teachers. When respondents were grouped according to Educational Attainment, plantilla position, and Family Income, it showed significant differences with the computed p -values of 0.000, 0.000, and 0.009, respectively, which are lower than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the hypothesis that reads "there is no significant difference in the level of performance of public elementary school teachers when grouped and compared according to Educational Attainment" is therefore "rejected."

Nonetheless, when respondents are grouped according to age, civil status, and length of service, the computed p -values of 0.631, 0.313, and 0.241, respectively, are all higher than the 0.05 level of significance, interpreted as not significant. Hence, the hypothesis that states "there is no significant difference in the level of

performance of public elementary school teachers when grouped and compared according to age, civil status, and length of service" is therefore accepted.

This suggests a positive correlation between three factors—educational attainment, plantilla position, and average family income of teachers—and their ability to perform effectively. Sumanga et al. (2022) affirm this in a study that revealed that educational attainment and the number of training attended were significant factors affecting teaching performance. Teachers who have completed more relevant training and have greater educational backgrounds typically have better teaching outcomes. Additionally, attending training sessions and pursuing higher education enhances the quality of teaching that is performed. This is supported by Marginson (2019), who suggests that education is an investment that improves individuals' skills, knowledge, and productivity. Teachers with higher levels of formal education might possess more advanced teaching techniques, subject matter expertise, and the ability to adapt to changing educational needs, potentially leading to enhanced teaching performance compared to those with low educational attainments. A research study reveals that there is a significant correlation between teacher salaries and performance. It highlights that the greater the teacher's salary, the more productivity and performance of teachers will increase. Therefore, teachers are becoming more productive and doing better the more money they receive (Safrudin, 2022).

Relationship Between the Levels of Occupational Stress and Performance of Public Elementary School Teachers

Table 9
Relationship Between the Levels of Occupational Stress and Performance of Public Elementary School Teachers

	<i>rho</i>	Sig Level	<i>p-value</i>	Interpretation
Level of Occupational Stress				
	-0.434	0.05	0.000	Significant
Level of Performance				

Table 9 summarizes the analysis between the level of occupational stress and the performance of public elementary school teachers, which shows a significant relationship, with a computed *p*-value of 0.000, which is lower than the 0.05 level of significance. Thus, the hypothesis that reads, "there is no relationship between the level of occupational stress and performance of public elementary school teachers" is therefore "rejected."

The result of the study implies that teachers' level of occupational stress has an impact on their teaching performance. In other words, the more stress a teacher is under, the more likely they are to experience a decline in their teaching performance. This finding is significant because it highlights the importance of considering the emotional and psychological well-being of teachers in addition to their academic and pedagogical qualifications. When teachers are experiencing high levels of stress, they may become less effective in their teaching roles, which can have negative consequences for student learning outcomes.

This confirms the study conducted by Zhao (2022), which concludes that there is a noteworthy correlation between teachers' job performance and occupational stress. Teachers who are under stress will perform poorly on the job. When this occurs, they'll likely exhibit undesirable behaviors, including being unmotivated and dissatisfied, making blunders at work, and acting violently. Furthermore, the effects of occupational stress that teachers face will highlight significant issues with their motivation, well-being, and educational quality. A research study highlights the predictor of teaching performance among the components of work-related stress. The study showed that low teaching effectiveness can result from increased demand, which is a component of stress. (Sarabia, 2020)

Conclusion

Teachers consistently excel in numerous facets of their roles, including delivering instruction, engaging students, managing the classroom, and promoting student learning and achievement. Management of instruction and working environment are two critical areas that can significantly impact teacher's daily work lives and, in turn, their mental health and well-being. Teachers who have lower educational attainment have shown higher levels of stress across all areas than those who have pursued further studies. These teachers may feel pressured to perform well to maintain their jobs or advance in their careers, which can lead to increased stress levels. The significant correlation between occupational stress and teacher performance shows how stress adversely affects various aspects of teaching. Addressing and mitigating occupational stress is crucial for maintaining high levels of teacher performance and ensuring positive educational outcomes for students. The results call for school heads to establish targeted support programs and professional development opportunities focused on stress management and stress coping strategies to educate teachers on effective techniques for handling the demands of their profession.

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